

Reproducibility study - Faster k-means cluster estimation

Faster K-Means Cluster Estimation

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we have tried to reproduce the experiments from the paper Faster K-Means Cluster Estimation [1]. Authors there present their work on improving popular clustering algorithm k-mean faster in terms of runtime speed while reaching comparable mean squared error (MSE) to the baseline implementation of K-Means speedup by triangle inequality [3].

The code and all 5 datasets were provided in authors github [2], however, modification was required in order to follow the procedure outlined in the paper. Due to long runtimes we focused only on the smallest 2 datasets.

In the end, we compared our results with the results provided from authors in the paper and noticed some inconsistencies with their claims. We tried different settings to explore where they might come from. In addition we have discovered a case where the proposed algorithm will not achieve suggested performance in reasonable time.

KEYWORDS

experiment, k-means, cluster, estimation, heuristic, reproducibility

1 Paper

1.1 Introduction

In the paper [1], authors present their work on improving popular clustering algorithm K-Means making it achieve comparable mean squared error (MSE) faster. They propose a fast heuristic to overcome the computation distance of each data point to each cluster centroid for every iteration with only marginal increase in MSE. Their heuristic predicts clusters, where a data point changes its membership only among a small subset of them - denoted as k' , by looking at nearby clusters after the first iteration of k-means. They state that their heuristic can be applied to different versions of the K-Means but results are presented

comparing it to K-Means sped up by triangle inequality. The results provided also show different seeding strategies for the initial centroids - random and K-Means++ [4].

Variable PIM indicates the increase of MSE of the solution found by the heuristic version relative to the non-heuristic one in percent. This is important to note as the authors claim that if the non-heuristic version runs in time T and achieves error, MSE, E their solution will run in time T' and achieve MSE of E' . The speedup presented is then T/T' and the PIM is calculated as $100*(E'-E)/E$.

1.3 Datasets

They present 5 datasets, which are synthetic or real-world, - Birch, Covtype, Mnist, KDDCup and Synthetic, see table 1. All datasets were available from their github [2].

Name	Cardinality	Dimensionality	Description
Birch	100000	2	10 by 10 grid of Gaussian clusters
Covtype	150000	55	Remote soil cover measurements
Mnist	60000	784	Original NIST handwritten digit training data
KDDCup	95412	481	KDD Cup 1998 data
Synthetic	100000	100	Uniform random dataset

Table 1: Used datasets

2 Strategy

We created an experiment runner for each dataset which accepts configuration and replicates the number of runs. For each configuration, which is written in the runner, it returns runtime and overall results for non-heuristic and heuristic cases using the same initial cluster centroids. The configuration has a format - k , K-means threshold, number

of centroids to remember, seed type, PIM, type of algorithm, where k is number of clusters and PIM is a percentage of an increase of MSE. Those configurations match the ones presented in the original paper in Table 2 and Table 3.

1.2 Algorithm

The experiment runner can be summarized in the following steps:

1. Initialize centroids (either random or K-Means++)
2. Run the non-heuristic version
3. Store runtime and the final MSE achieved
4. Calculate the MSE that the heuristic version should achieve (using MSE and PIM)
5. Execute the heuristic version with the target MSE and denote the time.
6. Repeat steps 1-5 until requested number of replicates is reached
7. Save the performance measures, as well as other execution information, explained later, to a file.

We also created the dataset wrappers that contain all experiment configurations for each of the datasets, load the dataset, only once, and run all of the configurations. For result comparison and evaluation we created a jupyter notebook that ingests the files created by the experiment runner, 1 file per configuration, and calculates the speedup.

3 Reproducibility

The source code for implementations of the non-heuristic implementation as well as the heuristic implementation was provided by the author on their github. Basic description of parameters of both of the methods were also denoted. The used datasets were also available in the same repository as already mentioned, thus coming in we gauged the chance of reproducibility as very high. However, we soon realized that the code does not execute with the latest version of python, 3.8.6, and python2 needs to be used instead, this was not indicated by the author in spite of python3 being around for more than 9 years at the time of the release of the paper.

With the strategy outlined above we were not able to reproduce the results. We realized that the reason why is a combination of multiple factors that we group into the following groups:

1. Settings - not specified by the author that affect the outcome.
2. Technical - code provided cannot be directly used to run the experiments as described in the paper, algorithm does not always achieve the advertised MSE
3. Non-technical - used machine performance and order of experiment execution unclear, one dataset description does not match the table in the paper

3.1 Settings

Only the relative speedup is reported by the author but no remark is done on the time both versions need to run in order to obtain the reported results. Longer runtime can be induced by smaller MSE increase between iterations, a parameter passable to the non-heuristic version. We noticed that the setup times for each of the versions differed and thus shorter runtimes would be more affected by this difference.

3.2 Technical

Both the heuristic and non-heuristic version had a stopping criterion set to percentual MSE decrease between subsequent iterations. However, if we aim to reproduce the speedup the stopping criterion for the heuristic version is tied to the error of the non-heuristic run via PMI. We modified the original code to stop once the MSE achieves the target MSE derived from non-heuristic run and the PMI.

Even with the stopping criterion described above we noticed that the algorithm does not behave as described in the paper. We noticed that in some cases the heuristic version never achieves the target MSE. There was no such remark in the original paper. In order to execute the runs we introduced additional alternate stopping criterion for the heuristic approach - MSE improvement percent between iterations. This value was set to either the absolute value of $PIM/10$ or if PMI was 0 to 0.01. The goal of this criterion is to detect when the algorithm stagnates and stop it. Those runs were reported as *stagnation* runs and will be discussed later in the results. To accommodate for those cases in our evaluation a flag whether this occurred is noted in the output file as well as the number of iterations each of the approaches performed, the final MSEs as well as the runtimes.

3.2 Non-Technical

We assumed that the runtime comparisons are a good way to report the improvement but were very short-sighted. Without additional information such as the machine specifications, memory, processors with caches, disk type, GPU and others the results are hardly reproducible. The order in which the experiments are executed might also have an impact on the results and this was not mentioned in the paper either. We had hoped to at the very least achieve the same speedup trends as described in the paper but this also proved to be troublesome.

In addition one of the datasets, Synthetic, did not have the same number of observations as stated 150,000 was reported in the paper but in reality it contains 581,012 observations. Furthermore additional information on how to process the datasets was not provided. This was mostly not an issue as datasets 1-4 were readable but dataset 5, synthetic, was serialized using pickle [5] and this was not

made clear. This is more of a future problem if pickle becomes deprecated.

5 Experiments and Results

In our experiments we focused on the 2 smallest of the datasets due to high experiment count per dataset - 10 experiments for varying k' , clusters to remember for the heuristic version as described in 1.1, and 8 for varying k , number of clusters. This results in 18 experiments per dataset. We also wanted to make sure that we get a somewhat representative sample of results and thus ran each experiment for the Birch dataset with 20 replicates and for the larger covtype with 10 replicates. High number of experiments and replicates resulted in long runtimes and we deemed the other datasets as infeasible with our resources, intel core i5 9th generation, 16 GB RAM (DDR4 2666Mhz), 500 GB SSD, Windows 10. GPU was not used. The Covtype dataset allocated 12 GB RAM and larger datasets resulted in swapping which would directly impact performance of the algorithms.

In the tables, Table 2A - Table 7B, we compare the results from the paper with the results we achieved. The *PMI*(%) is the increase in final MSE of the heuristic version compared to the non-heuristic one, The *Reported speedup* is the speedup stated in the paper, the *Measured speedup* is the speedup that we measured, averaged over the replicates that did not result in stagnation, and the *Stagnation* indicates the percentage of replicates that ended with outcome stagnation, as described in 3.1. The k corresponds to the total number of clusters, k' is the number of clusters that the heuristic version will check. *RND* and *KPP* refer to the seeding algorithm used for initial centroid locations and stand for random and K-Means++ respectively. The value in brackets for the *Measured speedup* is the standard deviation of the results we obtained. If this value is missing there was only a single replicate that did not stagnate thus it could not be calculated.

For the experiments with varying k' the k is kept at a constant 100, as given by the original paper, and for the experiments that vary k , the k' is always $0.4*k$, also as defined in the original paper.

The experiment runtimes were ranging from about 30 hours for Birch 3% MSE up to 48 hours for Covtype 1% MSE. Those runtimes aggregate all 18 experiments we performed per dataset per % MSE setting.

5.1 Birch with 3% MSE

5.1.1 Effects of varying k'

As the MSE percentage decrease between iterations to use was not explicitly stated in the paper we started off with 3%. We did manage to confirm that speedup occurs in some settings but even a slowdown can be observed with $k' \geq 40$. The measured speedup was not as significant as reported and the general trends, within RND or KPP settings, were not preserved either - for example for RND $k'=20$ the Measured speedup is smaller than for $k'=30$ whereas the Reported speedup is higher. We also observed an increased number of replicates that stagnated with the KPP seeding.

	$k' = 20$ RND	$k' = 20$ KPP	$k' = 30$ RND	$k' = 30$ KPP
PIM(%)	-0.11	0	0.04	0
Reported speedup	3.05	3.14	2.48	2.26
Measured speedup	1.19 (0.50)	1.21	1.65 (0.47)	1.03 (0.06)
Stagnation	35%	95%	25%	85%

Table 2A: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 3% MSE for varying k'

	$k' = 40$ RND	$k' = 40$ KPP	$k' = 50$ RND	$k' = 50$ KPP
PIM(%)	0	0	0	0
Reported speedup	2.01	1.93	1.68	1.67
Measured speedup	1.26 (0.41)	0.94 (0.11)	0.95 (0.35)	0.91 (0.16)
Stagnation	15%	55%	25%	60%

Table 2B: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 3% MSE for varying k'

	$k' = 60$ RND	$k' = 60$ KPP
PIM(%)	0	0
Reported speedup	1.41	1.31
Measured speedup	0.76 (0.48)	0.83 (0.08)
Stagnation	15%	55%

Table 2C: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 3% MSE for varying k'

5.1.2 Effects of varying k

In those experiments the stagnation proportion was much higher for the KPP seeding approach and barely any speedup was observed and most experiments ended in a longer runtime of the heuristic algorithm. On the other hand we observe a very small number of replicates that ended in stagnation for the RND setting.

	k = 50 RND	k = 50 KPP	k = 100 RND	k = 100 KPP
PIM(%)	0.31	0	0	0
Reported speedup	1.65	1.71	1.98	1.97
Measured speedup	0.91 (0.35)	1.00 (0.12)	1.26 (0.41)	0.94 (0.11)
Stagnation	20%	90%	15%	55%

Table 3A: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 3% MSE for varying k

	k = 500 RND	k = 500 KPP	k = 1000 RND	k = 1000 KPP
PIM(%)	0	0	0	0
Reported speedup	2.14	2.10	2.12	2.15
Measured speedup	0.13 (0.37)	0.97 (0.07)	1.25 (0.15)	0.82 (0.13)
Stagnation	0%	75%	0%	85%

Table 3B: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 3% MSE for varying k

5.2 Birch with 1% MSE

5.2.1 Effects of varying k'

We noticed that the runtimes might be too short and the initialization effect, mentioned in section 3.1, might have an impact. We decided to run the same set of experiments with a MSE percentage of 1 in order to extend the runtimes and diminish this effect in hopes of increasing the overall speedup.

We observed a result set closer resembling the speedup trends reported in the original paper, decreasing with increasing k'. However, our measured speedups did not achieve the same degree and the KPP setting still produced a high number of stagnation outcomes. In this case we observed fewer slowdowns than in the experiments with 3% MSE leading us to believe that the authors performed their experiments with even lower values of MSE decrease percentage.

	k' = 20 RND	k' = 20 KPP	k' = 30 RND	k' = 30 KPP
PIM(%)	-0.11	0	0.04	0
Reported speedup	3.05	3.14	2.48	2.26
Measured speedup	2.11 (0.75)	1.4	1.21 (0.77)	1.17 (0.11)
Stagnation	20%	95%	35%	85%

Table 4A: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 1% MSE for varying k'

	k' = 40 RND	k' = 40 KPP	k' = 50 RND	k' = 50 KPP
PIM(%)	0	0	0	0
Reported speedup	2.01	1.93	1.68	1.67
Measured speedup	1.12 (0.62)	1.10 (0.01)	1.40 (0.49)	0.89 (0.08)
Stagnation	20%	90%	45%	90%

Table 4B: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 1% MSE for varying k'

	k' = 60 RND	k' = 60 KPP
PIM(%)	0	0
Reported speedup	1.41	1.31
Measured speedup	1.00 (0.63)	0.82 (0.12)
Stagnation	30%	60%

Table 4C: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 1% MSE for varying k'

5.2.2 Effects of varying k

Compared to the 3% MSE experiments, 5.1.2, we observe more cases of speedup for both KPP and RND settings. This further implies that the authors intended their algorithm to be run with very low % MSE values. Only one of the experiments ended in a longer runtime of the heuristic algorithm. However, the KPP seeded variants still have a very high degree of stagnation.

	k = 50 RND	k = 50 KPP	k = 100 RND	k = 100 KPP
PIM(%)	0.31	0	0	0
Reported speedup	1.65	1.71	1.98	1.97
Measured speedup	1.42 (0.40)	1.14 (0.06)	1.12 (0.62)	1.10 (0.01)
Stagnation	30%	90%	20%	90%

Table 5A: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 1% MSE for varying k

	k = 500 RND	k = 500 KPP	k = 1000 RND	k = 1000 KPP
PIM(%)	0	0	0	0
Reported speedup	2.14	2.10	2.12	2.15
Measured speedup	1.56	1.03	1.40	0.63

	(0.31)	(0.20)	(0.28)	(0.18)
Stagnation	0%	75%	0%	90%

Table 5B: Reported and measured results for Birch dataset with 1% MSE for varying k

5.3 Covtype with 1% MSE

For the Covtype dataset with the lessons learnt from 5.2 we used 1% MSE.

5.3.1 Effects of varying k'

Yet again the speedup observed by us was nowhere near the reported and runs of the heuristic algorithm were again slower than the baseline for high values of k', following the suit with 5.1.1 and 5.2.1. It is worth noting that for this dataset we didn't get any stagnation outcomes for either of the seeding approaches.

	k' = 20 RND	k' = 20 KPP	k' = 30 RND	k' = 30 KPP
PIM(%)	0.21	0.03	0.02	0
Reported speedup	2.32	2.02	1.81	1.82
Measured speedup	1.23 (0.28)	1.17 (0.04)	1.06 (0.40)	1.04 (0.03)
Stagnation	0%	0%	0%	0%

Table 6A: Reported and measured results for Covtype dataset with 1% MSE for varying k'

	k' = 40 RND	k' = 40 KPP	k' = 50 RND	k' = 50 KPP
PIM(%)	0	0	0	0
Reported speedup	1.61	1.63	1.55	1.38
Measured speedup	1.06 (0.25)	0.99 (0.03)	1.13 (0.32)	0.95 (0.02)
Stagnation	0%	0%	0%	0%

Table 6B: Reported and measured results for Covtype dataset with 1% MSE for varying k'

	k' = 60 RND	k' = 60 KPP
PIM(%)	0	0
Reported speedup	1.42	1.20
Measured speedup	0.97 (0.33)	0.90 (0.01)
Stagnation	0%	0%

Table 6C: Reported and measured results for Covtype dataset with 1% MSE for varying k

5.3.2 Effects of varying k

Some of the measured results for the heuristic approach were again slower than the baseline. On the other hand we did not get almost any stagnation outcomes, apart for k=50. We also didn't observe the trend of increasing speedup with increasing k, as proportionally more and more clusters get ignored in the heuristic approach.

	k = 50 RND	k = 50 KPP	k = 100 RND	k = 100 KPP
PIM(%)	0.01	0.02	0.26	0
Reported speedup	1.35	1.31	1.65	1.50
Measured speedup	0.94 (0.24)	1.05 (0.07)	1.06 (0.25)	0.99 (0.03)
Stagnation	10%	0%	0%	0%

Table 7A: Reported and measured results for Covtype dataset with 1% MSE for varying k

	k = 500 RND	k = 500 KPP	k = 1000 RND	k = 1000 KPP
PIM(%)	0	0	0	0
Reported speedup	1.94	1.87	1.97	1.90
Measured speedup	1.28 (0.16)	1.06 (0.04)	1.27 (0.10)	1.10 (0.03)
Stagnation	0%	0%	0%	0%

Table 7B: Reported and measured results for Covtype dataset with 1% MSE for varying k

5.4 Statistical Testing

The paper did not provide any significance tests with regards to the PIM or the runtimes. Only a single value was provided and we assumed this was the mean speedup across multiple replicates. For our significance tests we used a set of relative speedups, calculated for each replicate separately. Only replicates that did not result in stagnation were used as the original paper did not state anything about the stagnation. As we had no information from the author other than a single value, assuming mean, we used t-test to calculate the likelihood of obtaining the reported speedup for each experiment. We used 2 approaches, one only using our replicates and a second one using the Central Limit theorem to sample from our relative speedup set with N=50, repeated 1000 times, to obtain a reasonably normally distributed set. Both of the tests were used in conjunction to arrive at the decision (All cases ended up being unanimous). For some of the experiment configurations where all but one replicates resulted in stagnation, for instance Table4A with k'=20 and

KPP, we could not perform those tests. Alpha of 0.05 was used for all of our significance testing.

All of our measured speedups were significantly different from the reported results. However, we made a lot of assumptions, such as the reported speedup being a mean of all speedups, as well as having very few replicates that did not stagnate in our runs in some cases. Furthermore as already discussed the speedup, albeit relative, is very dependent on factors not specified by the author so it was very likely to obtain significant results.

[5] <https://docs.python.org/3/library/pickle.html>

[6] <https://github.com/e11938258/experiment-reproduction-faster-k-means>

CONCLUSION

Our attempt to reproduce the results of the paper was partly successful but the journey was not straightforward. The provided code was very useful in spite of the need to be modified in order to verify the claims in the paper but it was present which is not the case for many papers. The used data was also available though some metadata was missing, such as how to load the datasets and how to extract the subset which was used in the paper in case of the Synthetic dataset. The greatest hindrance to reproducibility we experienced was the not stated value of the MSE decrease between iterations which resulted in costly guesswork on our side. The final results and the approach we took with initial setting and further adjustment of the value was based solely on our assumptions.

We managed to reproduce some of the trends described on the paper such as decrease in speedup with increasing k' in most cases and decrease in speedup with increasing k . On the other hand we did not manage to confirm the claim that the heuristic algorithm jumps local minima and will only have more iterations when it approaches lower MSE. On the contrary we found that in some cases the algorithm doesn't manage to finish, in a reasonable time of at least 4 hours, when the non-heuristic version runs for about a minute.

The code to execute our experiments can be found on our github. [6]

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